

Effect of Temperature on Selective Adsorption by Silica Gel from Binary Mixtures.

BY M. R. ASWATHANARAYANA RAO.

Selective adsorption from binary mixtures has been investigated by a number of workers (Williams, *Medd. K. Vetenskapsakad. Nobel-Inst.*, 1913, No. 23; Ostwald and Izaguirre, *Kolloid Z.*, 1922, 30, 279; Jones and Outridge, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1574; Bartell and Scheffler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 2507; Rao, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1932, 36, 615). There is no published work, however, on the effect of temperature on selective adsorption. Investigations on the effect of temperature on selectivity are described in the present paper. The term selectivity is given by the equation,

$$S = m (C_1 - C_2) / g$$

where S denotes selectivity (apparent adsorption); m , weight of the liquid mixture added to the gel; g , weight of the gel in equilibrium with the liquid; C_1 , the initial concentration of the selectively adsorbed component; C_2 , the equilibrium concentration of the same component, C_1 and C_2 being expressed in weight fraction.

Mixtures which have the **U** and **S**-shaped curves (when selectivity is plotted against C_2) were used to study the variation of selectivity with temperature. For **U**-shaped curves binary mixtures of benzene with (a) alcohol, and (b) heptane were used. For the **S**-shaped curves mixtures of pyridine and water were employed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The organic liquids were purified by the usual methods employed in organic chemistry. The purity was further tested by finding out the refractive indices before and after shaking them with the gel. It was found that there was no change. The gel used was prepared in this laboratory by the method of McGavack and Patrick (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 951). The moisture content was 3.36 % and the gel adsorbed 0.362 c.c. of benzene from the saturated vapour.

Curves 1-3 represent benzene-heptane at 30°, 74° and 98° respectively and curve 4 for benzene-alcohol at 30°.

⊙ ⊙ ⊙ points for S at 63°.

. . . „ „ at 98°.

Figure 2 shows the type of vessel used to carry out the selective adsorption measurements. The side reservoir R, served to transfer the liquid from the bulb B when the equilibrium was attained. The dry vessel was weighed before and after the introduction of the activated gel. After cooling the bulb in ice for some time, the mixture was introduced into it by means of a narrow funnel whose lower end was about one cm. above the level of the gel in the bulb. This prevented the liquid sticking to the sides of the vessel. Care was taken to see that neither the gel nor the liquid entered the reservoir. The bulb was weighed and sealed off at S, and kept vertically in a water thermostat for 30 hours to attain equilibrium. The liquid did not condense in the reservoir at the end of this period. The vessel was then tilted and the equilibrium mixture separated from the gel by allowing the liquid to flow into R. It was then taken out of the thermostat and allowed to cool. The side tube was cut off, and the composition of the liquid in the reservoir was found using a Pulfrich Refractometer. A blank experiment showed that there was no change in concentration when two solutions (of different concentrations) were placed one in the reservoir and the other in the bulb and heated to 97° for half an hour. The following results were obtained.

TABLE I.

Mixture used = benzene and heptane. Selectively adsorbed component = benzene. C'_2 = % wt. of benzene in the equilibrium mixture.

30°		74°		98°	
C'_2 .	$S \times 100.$	C'_2 .	$S \times 100.$	C'_2 .	$S \times 100.$
2.0	4.30	8.4	7.03	9.0	6.42
...	18.2	8.50
4.8	6.56	28.0	9.61	29.2	9.10
7.0	7.96	37.9	9.86	47.3	8.34
10.0	9.72	46.4	8.86	60.1	7.17
19.5	11.65	60.9	7.24	70.6	5.33
41.8	11.53	70.6	5.75	79.8	3.45
64.4	7.19	91.2	0.82	90.8	0.67
80.4	4.56
94.3	1.06

TABLE II.

Mixture used = benzene and alcohol. Selectively adsorbed component = alcohol. C'_2 = % wt. of alcohol in the equilibrium mixture.

30°		63°		98°	
C'_2 .	$S \times 100.$	C'_2 .	$S \times 100.$	C'_2 .	$S \times 100.$
0.4	12.80	1.6	11.77	19.5	17.80
2.6	19.00	3.0	17.34	42.65	13.25
6.1	20.84	6.3	20.72	54.4	9.39
11.0	20.20	18.8	18.30	68.9	5.18
18.4	18.90	53.1	9.56	84.3	2.56
42.6	12.06	68.2	5.38	94.1	0.74
68.6	5.36	84.7	2.29
81.6	2.27	94.0	0.81
24.1	0.32

TABLE III.

Mixture used = pyridine and water. $C'_2 = \%$ weight of pyridine in the equilibrium mixture.

30°		74°		98°	
C'_2 .	$S \times 100$.	C'_2 .	$S \times 100$.	C'_2 .	$S \times 100$.
4.2	11.7	5.8	8.17	7.2	5.57
11.6	15.30	12.6	12.57	15.4	8.07
27.4	13.22	20.9	12.01	30.9	8.66
46.2	7.94	45.2	7.97	46.7	5.56
63.1	3.03	62.6	3.33	63.6	1.59
77.5	0.26	77.4	0.38	81.7	-0.21
81.7	-0.40	84.9	-0.44	85.1	-0.86
85.2	-1.03	90.7	-1.67	90.5	-1.21
90.8	-1.94	95.6	-1.87	95.6	-1.75
95.8	-2.23	98.5	-1.59	98.4	-1.31
98.6	-1.90

DISCUSSION.

It is clear from Figs. 1 and 3 that as the temperature increases, the selectivity decreases. The decrease depends upon the particular mixture used. Thus in the case of alcohol-benzene mixtures, the points obtained for selectivity at higher temperatures lie so close to the curve at 30° that no attempt is made to draw the curve through these points. It is also evident that the decrease in selectivity does not depend upon the magnitude of selectivity although the maximum values at various temperatures occur at almost the same equilibrium concentration. Thus in the case of benzene-alcohol mixtures, the maximum for selectivity at 33° is 0.208 while the difference in selectivity values at 30° and 60° is only 0.006. In the case of benzene-heptane mixtures, the maximum selectivity is 0.117 but the difference between the two selectivity values is about 0.02 for the same two temperatures and at the same equilibrium concentration of 6% benzene by weight. The maximum value of selectivity occurs at about 38% benzene-heptane

mixtures for all temperatures. In the case of alcohol-benzene mixtures this value occurs at 6% alcohol concentration.

FIG. 3.

1-3 represent $S - C_2$ curves at 30° , 74° and 98° respectively.

FIG. 4_s

1-4 represents $\log S - 1/T$ curves when C_2 equals 0.10, 0.15, 0.20 and 0.25 respectively.

Figure 3 represents the S-shaped curve obtained with pyridine-water mixtures. The remarks made in the previous paragraph apply to this also. It is of interest to know whether the point of zero selectivity

(at about 78.6 % of pyridine) remains at the same equilibrium concentration at all temperatures. In the experiments that were tried it was found that this point was almost identical. Thus at 30° the zero selectivity occurred at 78.45 % pyridine concentration whereas at 98° it occurred at 78.0 %.

A relationship can be deduced between selectivity and the amount of selectively adsorbed liquid by taking benzene-alcohol mixture into consideration. It has already been pointed out that alcohol is selectively adsorbed at all concentrations. Let m/g in the selectivity formula (formula I) be designated M . When equilibrium has attained, let C_g be the concentration of alcohol (in weight fraction) in the liquid adsorbed by the gel and let m' be the weight of the mixture adsorbed by 1 g. of the gel. It is clear that

$$M(C_1) = (M - m') C_2 + m' C_g$$

$$\text{or } M(C_1 - C_2) = m' (C_g - C_2) = \text{Selectivity.} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

Thus selectivity represents the excess of alcohol adsorbed by 1 g. of the gel (owing to the selective nature of adsorption) over what would have been present if there were no preferential adsorption. Hence for an increase in selectivity at the same equilibrium concentration C_2 , either m' or C_g should increase. But the increase in m' is comparatively small and hence C_g must increase for an increase in selectivity.

It is usually assumed that the surface of the gel is responsible for the greater adsorption of alcohol (Jones and Outridge, *loc. cit.*). It has also been shown that selectivity is a single-valued function of the equilibrium concentration whether the experiment is done in the vapour phase or in the liquid phase. The mechanism of selective adsorption of alcohol on silica gel from a binary mixture of alcohol and benzene is analogous to that of the adsorption of a single gas or vapour and the formula derived for the latter phenomenon is applied to the selective adsorption of alcohol.

According to Williams (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1919, **A**, 96, 287, 298)

$$\log \frac{x}{C} = K_1 + K_2/T$$

where x denotes amount of the gas (in moles) adsorbed per unit weight of the solid; $C=1/V$, the conc. of the gas; T , absolute temperature; K_1 and K_2 being constants.

Henry (*Phil. Mag.*, 1922, 44, 68) arrived at an identical formula from entirely different assumptions based on the reasoning of Langmuir. Applying this equation we get

$$x = C \cdot e^{k_1 + \frac{k_2}{T}}$$

where x = amount of alcohol in moles adsorbed per unit weight of the gel ; $C = C_2$, the equilibrium conc. K_1 and K_2 are constants.

Combining this with Eq. (ii) we get

$$\begin{aligned} S = m' C_g - m' C_2 &= K C_2 \cdot e^{k_1 + \frac{k_2}{T}} - m' C_2 \text{ (where } K \text{ is a constant).} \\ &= C_2 \left(K e^{k_1 + \frac{k_2}{T}} - m' \right) \quad \dots \text{ (iii)} \end{aligned}$$

The above equation indicates that selectivity decreases with rise in temperature. This equation, it must be noted, applies to dilute solutions only.

In the equation (iii) if C_2 is constant, the variation of m' with temperature is comparatively small; since the volume of the liquid adsorbed by a porous substance is fairly constant at all temperatures (*cf.* McBain, "Sorption of Gases and Vapours", p. 486). Hence when C_2 is small, a straight line should be obtained when $\log S$ is plotted against $1/T$. The following values are obtained from the benzene-heptane curves at different temperatures. S_1 , S_2 and S_3 are the selectivity values at 30°, 74° and 98° respectively.

TABLE IV.

$C_2 \times 100.$	$\log S_1 \times 100.$	$\log S_2 \times 100.$	$\log S_3 \times 100.$
10	0.8325	0.8774	0.9823
20	0.9030	0.9415	1.0414
20	0.9405	0.9694	1.0682
25	0.9562	0.9814	1.0930

$$\frac{1}{T_1} = 0.3301 \times 10^{-2},$$

$$\frac{1}{T_2} = 0.2382 \times 10^{-2},$$

$$\frac{1}{T_3} = 3.2699 \times 10^{-2}.$$

In Fig 4, the values of S_1 , S_2 and S_3 are plotted against $1/T_1$, $1/T_2$ and $1/T_3$ respectively. Straight lines are got in every case as predicted by the equation (iii).

Equation (iii) has been derived for a **U**-shaped curve. The **S**-shaped curve can be considered as being made up of two **U**-shaped curves each representing the selectivity of one of the components. The same equation can therefore be applied in explaining the decrease in selectivity with rise in temperature.

SUMMARY.

1. The variation of selective adsorption with temperature has been measured using silica gel with the following mixtures:—(i) benzene-heptane, (ii) alcohol-benzene, and (iii) pyridine-water, over entire range of concentrations.

2. It has been found that the selectivity decreases with a rise in temperature.

3. An equation has been derived to explain the observed changes in selectivity.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
CENTRAL COLLEGE, UNIVERSITY OF MYSORE,
BANGALORE.

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